

Studies on Manganese Ferrocyanide Sol. Part II. Kinetics of Slow Coagulation by Viscometric Method

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Kinetics of slow coagulation of manganese ferrocyanide sol in the light of Bhattacharya's equation has been studied using viscometric method. The values of the relevant constants of the equation have been calculated for LiCl and KCl.

Slow coagulation of the sols with electrolytes has been studied in detail by several workers; but relatively little work has been done on the influence of the concentration of the coagulant electrolyte on the coagulation time of sols. Paine¹ has shown that the time of coagulation t , is a function of the electrolyte concentration c ($t = K/C^2$ where K and P are constants). Dumanski and Scherschnev² also expressed this in the form $t = ac^n$ (a and n are constants). Mathews and Murphy³ and also Boutarie⁴ found that for every electrolyte there was a limiting concentration below which coagulation was not possible. In spite of the extensive work, the fact remains that no suitable expression is found in the literature which can be widely used. Recently Bhattacharya and co-workers⁵⁻⁷ studied the variation of the time of coagulation with the electrolyte concentration of a number of sols and suggested a general equation:

$$c = a + \frac{m \times 1/t}{n + 1/t} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

(where a , m and n are constants). This equation represents a hyperbola between c and $1/t$, but when the constant n becomes very large as compared to $1/t$, the equation takes the form:

$$c = a + \frac{m}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{t} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

linear between a/c and $1/t$

Bhattacharya *et al.*⁵⁻⁷ claim that their equation agrees fairly well with the experimental data of different authors working in the field. Upadhyaya and Mushran⁸ have discussed the applicability of Bhattacharya's equation during the slow gelation of some

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2. *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 62, 187.
3. *Science*, 1921, 43, 581.
4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1928, 43, 146.
5. *This Journal* 1961, 28, 179, 638; 1962, 29, 687, 769; 1963, 30, 361
6. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1965, 10, 561.
7. *Kolloid Z.*, 1966, 141, 95.
8. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1966, 11, 124.
9. *This Journal*, 1968, 35, 234.
10. *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, 178, 170.

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succinate sols. Agarwal and Mushran¹¹ have studied the stability of some gel, yielding metal-organic sols using this equation. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay¹² have derived the same equation from the equation of Reerink³ which has got a theoretical basis. Hence Bhattacharya's equation can also be considered as having some theoretical basis.

In view of the above, an attempt has been made to study the kinetics of slow coagulation of manganese ferrocyanide sol in the light of Bhattacharya's equation, using viscometric method. The values of constant a , m and n have been calculated for lithium chloride and potassium chloride at $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

EXPERIMENTAL

The manganese ferrocyanide sol was prepared by mixing potassium ferrocyanide and manganese chloride (both B.D.H. AnalaR) as described previously¹⁴. Viscosity measurements were made by modified Scarpa's method.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ The temperature was controlled at $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ using a Gallenkamp thermostat. All these operations were carried out in a dark room, using red lamp, as dilute aqueous solution of potassium ferrocyanide undergoes photoreaction on exposure to sunlight as reported by Asperger¹⁶.

From the inflections in viscosity—time curves the value of t was determined by adding different concentration of electrolyte, as shown by Bhattacharya⁷. Hence different mixtures of varying compositions were used, keeping total volume 20 ml in all the cases. The observations are recorded in Table I (A and B) and II for lithium chloride and potassium chloride respectively.

The reciprocals of the different time $1/t$ corresponding to the point of inflexion were plotted against the respective concentration c . By extrapolation of $c-1/t$ curves, the value of the constant a , critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol, when $1/t=0$ were obtained. The value of c being known, the $(c-a)^{-1}$ was found out, which was then plotted against t . The intercept on the $(c-a)^{-1}$ axis provides $1/m$ and the tangent of the angle on the t axis, n/m , from which m and n are evaluated.

TABLE IA
Manganese ferrocyanide per litre of the sol=3.8 g.

Mixtures	*c.	Time corres. t	1/t	*a	c-a	1/c-a
Slow Coagulation with LiCl.						
1	294.0	12	83.33×10^{-3}	60	234	4.273×10^{-3}
2	264.8	18.	55.55	60	194.8	5.138
3	235.2	21.8	45.87	60	175.2	5.707
4	215.6	25.5	39.21	60	155.6	6.428
5	198.0	30.2	33.11	60	138.0	7.253

*Expressed in mM/litre

m = 458.6 mM/litre.

n = 0.0761 min⁻¹

11. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 343.

12. *Ibid.*, 1959, 38, 811.

13. "Colloid Science", Vol. 1, 1952, edited by Kruyt, p. 310.

14. Joshi, and Hari Mohan, *This Journal*

15. *Gazette*, 1910, 40, 271.

16. Asperger, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 48, 617.

TABLE IB
Slow Coagulation with KCl.

Mixtures	$\%a$	Time corres. t	$1/t$	$\%a$	$c-a$	$1/c-a$
1	100	12.5	80.00	25	75	13.33
2	90	16.1	62.11	25	65	15.38
3	80	20.0	50.00	25	55	18.18
4	70	26.5	37.73	25	45	22.22
5	60	35.5	28.16	25	35	28.57

$m=217.4 \text{ mM/litre}$

$n=0.1444 \text{ min}^{-1}$

DISCUSSION

The graphs of c against $1/t$ drawn from the experimental data, are of hyperbolic nature (Fig. 1). The relation between $(c-a)^{-1}$ of electrolyte and their respective time of coagulation were found to be linear (Fig. 2) and Fig 3 according to the relation:

$$(c-a)^{-1} = \frac{nt}{m} + \frac{1}{m} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

derived from Bhattacharya equation.

Fig. 1 (a) Coagulation with LiCl
(b) Coagulation with KCl

FIG. 2. Coagulation with LiCl

Fig. 3 Coagulation with KCl

If $1/t$ tends to zero, equation(1) reduces $c=a$, which means that a is the concentration of the electrolyte coagulating the sol in infinite time. Alternatively, the sol can remain stable in presence of concentration given by a , the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol; a represents the same limiting concentration for every electrolyte below which coagulation is not possible, as indicated by Mathews and Murphy,³ Boutaric⁴ and others. The value of the constant a was found to be 80.0 mM/litre in case of LiCl and 25 mM/litre for KCl. This difference of coagulation concentration indicates the stability of the sol towards these electrolytes.

When $1/t$ is very large as compared to κ , i.e. when t is very small, as happens in the rapid coagulation region, κ can be neglected in equation (1) so that $c=a+m$ or more strictly $c-a \rightarrow m$ in the zone of rapid coagulation. Hence ' m ' represents the concentration of the electrolyte above the critical stability concentration value ' a ' which will produce instantaneous coagulation. In other words, we may say that at $c=a+m$, the region of slow coagulation merges into the rapid coagulation. The value of m was found to be 458.6 mM/litre for LiCl and 217.4 mM/litre for KCl. These values represent the amount of excess of the electrolyte that should be added above the critical stability concentration in order to cause the immediate coagulation of the manganese ferrocyanide sol.

The value of κ was found to be 0.0761 min^{-1} for LiCl and 0.1444 min^{-1} for KCl. The physical significance of κ is difficult to describe as it seems to depend on such factors as frequency of collisions, thickness of double layer, charge neutralization, and zeta-potential etc. which are responsible for the sol to the electrolyte. Further study on ' κ ' from the point of view of coagulation and stability of the sols is likely to supply revealing and interesting information. Further work in this line is in progress.

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